

Yield loss caused by leaffolder (LF) damage alone and combined with yellow stem borer (YSB) damage

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LF *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* (Gn.) and YSB *Scirpophaga incertulas* (Wlk.) are major pests of rice in Gujarat. We estimated yield loss caused by LF infestation alone and in combination with YSB infestation during 1986 summer and kharif seasons. Commercially grown cultivar GR11 was the test variety. Fifty plants were observed periodically for infestation by

Regression of grain yield on LF infestation (a) and on combined LF and YSB infestation in summer (b) and in kharif (c) Gujarat, India, 1986.

LF alone and 50 for infestation by LF and YSB (whiteheads). Grain was collected from individual plants.

Regressions of grain yield by percentage LF infestation alone and percentage LF and YSB infestation were calculated (see figure). For every unit of

increase in LF infestation alone, yield decreased 1.4% during summer and 1.46% during kharif. For every unit of increase in LF and YSB infestation, yield decreased 1.12% during summer and 1.27% during kharif. □

Spiders in Madhya Pradesh, India

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Weekly surveys were made of spiders contributing to rice pest control from the nursery stage until harvest in the rice zone (Chhattishgarh region) of Madhya Pradesh during 1984-86 rabi (Jan-May) and kharif (Jul-Nov). Nearly 10 ha were sampled weekly. At the early crop stages, spiders were collected by 100 sweeps/ha of a sweep net swinging through 180° with a 150-cm radius and covering $350 \text{ cm}^2/\text{sweep}$. From panicle initiation onward, spiders were sampled using $70 \times 30\text{-cm}$ plastic bags. The bag was held horizontally beside the rice hill to be sampled, and the hill was struck firmly four times so that spiders fell into the bag. About 250 hills were sampled

Spiders recorded in Madhya Pradesh, India, 1984-86.

Spider	Family
<i>Neoscona</i> sp.	Araneidae
<i>Runcinia</i> sp.	Thomisidae
<i>Thornisus</i> sp.	Thomisidae
<i>Arctosa</i> sp.	Lycosidae
<i>Pardosa</i> sp.	Lycosidae
<i>Tetragnatha</i> sp.	Tetragnathidae
<i>Oxyopes</i> sp.	Oxyopidae
<i>Uloborid</i> sp.	Uloboridae
<i>Eusparassid</i> sp.	Eusparassidae
<i>Aelurillus</i> sp.	Salticidae
<i>Bianor</i> sp.	Salticidae
<i>Hyllus</i> sp.	Salticidae
<i>Thyene</i> sp.	Salticidae

each week. The Commonwealth Agricultural Bureaux International Institute of Entomology at the British Museum, London, identified the spiders (see table). This is the first record of spiders in Chhattishgarh region. □

Rice thrips, a new rice pest in Northern Telangana, India

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Incidence of rice thrips *Stenchaetothrips biformis* (Bagn), hitherto a minor pest of rice, was severe in the Jul-Nov crop in the Northern Telangana zone of Andhra Pradesh, especially during Aug-Sep. Incidence also was severe in about 100 ha of rice planted during the last week of Aug. Farmers in this area normally sow in Jun and transplant in Jul. In 1986, sowing was delayed by the late onset of monsoon. The normal cropping pattern is rice - rice.

Thrips damage was severe during a prolonged dry spell after the onset of the monsoon. The late rice was more prone to pest infestation than the early crop. Typical symptoms were inward leaf rolling, wilting, and fine yellowish or silvery longitudinal streaks developing from the margin to the midrib.

Thrips damage was severe in transplanted Surekha, followed by IR50, WGL 22245, BPT1235, and WGL 3996. Incidence was lowest in WGL 44645.

One-month-old nurseries of IET1994, IR20, IET9553, IR36, IET8906, IET8559, TN1, and IET9999 were severely infested when sown in late Aug. Temperatures during Aug were $23.9\text{--}32.2^\circ\text{C}$, with a mean rainfall of 70.8 mm. The same cultures transplanted in plots suffered pest